

Notes and calculations

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Four terminal QD as efficient
charge and heat current
rectifier

09/2022 -

a) Non-equilibrium GFS and
calculation of correlators $\sim \sum_{\lambda \mu} \frac{V_{\lambda \mu} \langle c_{\lambda 0}^{\dagger} c_{\mu 0} \rangle}{\epsilon - \epsilon_{\lambda \mu} + i0}$

b) crucial, exact relation between
GZ and average charge on a dot,
current in one of the leads

c) some test results of numerical
evaluation

loop on the contour

(a)

Def.

Keldysh functions
and averages $\sum_k \frac{V_k \langle C_{N+1}^{\dagger} \rangle}{\epsilon - \epsilon_{k\sigma} + i0}$

$$G(t, t') = -i \langle T_C [\Psi_H(t) \Psi_H^{\dagger}(t')] \rangle$$

$\Psi_H(t), \Psi_H^{\dagger}(t')$ fermion field operators in the Heisenberg picture

contour ordered GF plays an analogous role in the non-equilibrium theory as the causal Green function plays in equilibrium theory

then if

$$G^<(t, t') = +i \langle \Psi_H^{\dagger}(t') \Psi_H(t) \rangle = \langle\langle \Psi_H^{\dagger}(t') | \Psi_H(t) \rangle\rangle^<$$

needed, one calculates time ordered

$$G(t, t') = -i \langle T_t [\Psi_H(t) \Psi_H^{\dagger}(t')] \rangle = \langle\langle \Psi_H(t) | \Psi_H^{\dagger}(t') \rangle\rangle^<$$

time ordering

$$T\{A(t)B(t')\} = \theta(t-t')A(t)B(t') \mp \theta(t'-t)B(t')A(t)$$

$$\theta(t-t') = \begin{cases} 1 & t > t' \\ 0 & t < t' \end{cases}$$

Keldysh GFs in equilibrium

(1)

spectral function:

$$A(k, \omega) = i(G^>(k, \omega) - G^<(k, \omega)) = i[G^>(k, \omega) - G^<(k, \omega)]$$

fluctuation-dissipation theorem:

$$G^<(k, \omega) = i f(\omega) A(k, \omega)$$

$$G^>(k, \omega) = -i (1 - f(\omega)) A(k, \omega)$$

Definitions

$$T\{A(t) B(t')\} = \theta(t - t') A(t) B(t') - \theta(t' - t) B(t') A(t)$$

$$\Psi_H(t) = e^{iHt/\hbar} \Psi(0) e^{-iHt/\hbar}$$

$$\langle n(x) \rangle = \langle \Psi^\dagger(x) \Psi(x) \rangle =$$

$$= -i\hbar G(x, t; x, t^+) \quad ; \quad t^+ = \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} (t + \epsilon)$$

$$\langle n(x) \rangle = -i G^<(x, t; x, t)$$

$$G(k, \omega) = \int d^3x \int dt e^{i\omega(t-t')} e^{-ik(x-x')} G(x-x', t-t')$$

$$\Psi(x, t) \rightarrow \Psi(t)$$

$$\theta(t - t') = \begin{cases} 1 & t > t' \\ 0 & t < t' \end{cases}$$

$$G^>(t, t') = -i\theta(t - t') \langle \{\Psi(t), \Psi^\dagger(t')\} \rangle$$

$$G^<(t, t') = i\theta(t - t') \langle [\Psi(t), \Psi^\dagger(t')] \rangle$$

$$G^<(t, t') = i \langle \Psi^\dagger(t') \Psi(t) \rangle$$

$$G^>(t, t') = -i \langle \Psi(t) \Psi^\dagger(t') \rangle$$

$$\boxed{G^> - G^< = G^> - G^<} \quad \text{always}$$

Define

Oblinanie srednich nraznyeh! Sisty
nykh dlya $\Gamma(E) = \Gamma$

$$P_{\sigma}(\omega) \equiv \sum_{\lambda k} \frac{V_{\lambda k \sigma}^* \langle d_{\sigma}^{\dagger} c_{\lambda k \sigma} \rangle}{\omega - \epsilon_k + i\delta}$$

$$= \sum_{\lambda k} \frac{V_{\lambda k \sigma}^*}{\omega - \epsilon_k + i\delta} \left[V_{\lambda k \sigma} f_{\lambda}(\epsilon_k) g_{\sigma}^a(\epsilon_k) + \int_{\mathbb{R}} \frac{d\omega'}{2\pi i} \frac{g_{\sigma}^s(\omega')}{\omega' - \epsilon_k + i\delta} \right]$$

$$= \sum_{\lambda k} \frac{|V_{\lambda k \sigma}|^2}{\omega - \epsilon_k + i\delta} f_{\lambda}(\epsilon_k) g_{\sigma}^a(\epsilon_k)$$

$$+ \sum_{\lambda k} \frac{|V_{\lambda k \sigma}|^2}{\omega - \epsilon_k + i\delta} \int \frac{d\omega'}{2\pi i} \frac{g_{\sigma}^s(\omega')}{\omega' - \epsilon_k + i\delta}$$

$$= \sum_{\lambda k} \int \frac{|V_{\lambda k \sigma}|^2}{\omega - \epsilon + i\delta} \delta(\epsilon - \epsilon_{\lambda k}) f_{\lambda}(\epsilon) g_{\sigma}^a(\epsilon) d\epsilon$$

$$= \int d\epsilon \sum_{\lambda} \dots$$

$$\Gamma_{\lambda \sigma}(\epsilon) \equiv 2\pi \sum_{\mathbb{R} k} |V_{\lambda k \sigma}|^2 \delta(\epsilon - \epsilon_{\lambda k})$$

$$= \sum_{\lambda} \frac{\Gamma_{\lambda}(\epsilon)}{2\pi} \int d\epsilon \frac{f_{\lambda}(\epsilon) g_{\sigma}^a(\epsilon)}{\omega - \epsilon + i\delta}$$

$$+ \int d\epsilon \frac{\Gamma_{\lambda \sigma}(\epsilon)}{2\pi} \frac{1}{\omega - \epsilon + i\delta} \int \frac{d\omega'}{2\pi i} \frac{g_{\sigma}^s(\omega')}{\omega' - \epsilon + i\delta}$$

$$= \sum_{\lambda} \Gamma_{\lambda \sigma} \int \frac{d\epsilon}{2\pi} \frac{f_{\lambda}(\epsilon) g_{\sigma}^a(\epsilon)}{\omega - \epsilon + i\delta}$$

$$+ \int \frac{d\epsilon}{2\pi} \int \frac{d\omega'}{2\pi i} \frac{\Gamma_{\lambda \sigma}(\epsilon) g_{\sigma}^s(\omega')}{(\omega - \epsilon + i\delta)(\omega' - \epsilon + i\delta)}$$

IMBL $\rho_{\lambda\sigma}(\epsilon) = \rho_{\lambda\sigma}$

$$-i \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{d\epsilon}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{d\omega'}{2\pi} \frac{g_{\sigma}^{\lambda}(\omega')}{\omega - \omega'} \left[\frac{1}{\omega - \epsilon + i\gamma} - \frac{1}{\omega' - \epsilon + i\gamma} \right] \rightarrow 0 \quad ?$$

$$\omega - \epsilon + i\gamma - \omega' + \epsilon - i\gamma$$

$$\frac{1}{x + \omega' - \epsilon + i\gamma} - \frac{1}{\omega' - \epsilon + i\gamma}$$

$$\frac{-1}{(x + \omega' - \epsilon)^2 + \gamma^2} \rightarrow 0$$

$$\rho_{\sigma}(\omega) = \sum_{\lambda} \rho_{\lambda\sigma} \int \frac{d\epsilon}{2\pi} \frac{f_{\lambda}(\epsilon) g_{\sigma}^{\lambda}(\epsilon)}{\omega - \epsilon + i\gamma}$$

$$\text{Im} \rho_{\sigma}(\omega + i\gamma) = -\pi \sum_{\lambda, \kappa} V_{\lambda\kappa\sigma}^* \langle d_{\sigma}^{\dagger} c_{\lambda\kappa\sigma} \rangle \delta(\omega - \epsilon_{\lambda\kappa})$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\epsilon \frac{1}{\omega - \epsilon + i\gamma} - \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\epsilon \frac{1}{\omega' - \epsilon + i\gamma}$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{\omega - \epsilon}{(\omega - \epsilon)^2 + \gamma^2} d\epsilon - \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{\omega' - \epsilon}{(\omega' - \epsilon)^2 + \gamma^2} d\epsilon$$

non-equilibrium

min noise, same!

$$\langle d | d^\dagger \rangle = g^i$$

$$\langle b | b^\dagger \rangle = g^i$$

$$b_{-\sigma} = \sum_{\lambda k} V_{\lambda k - \sigma}^* \langle d_{-\sigma}^\dagger c_{\lambda k - \sigma} \rangle =$$

$$= -i \sum_{\lambda k} V_{\lambda k - \sigma}^* \int \frac{d\omega}{2\pi} \langle c_{\lambda k - \sigma} | d_{-\sigma}^\dagger \rangle_{\omega}^<$$

$$= -i \sum_{\lambda k} V_{\lambda k - \sigma}^* V_{\lambda k - \sigma} \int \frac{d\omega}{2\pi} \left(g_{\lambda k}^{(0)r}(\omega) g_{\sigma}^{<}(\omega) + g_{\lambda k}^{(0)<}(\omega) g_{\sigma}^a(\omega) \right)$$

$$g_{\lambda k}^{(0)<}(\omega) = 2\pi i f_{\lambda}(\omega) \delta(\omega - \epsilon_{\lambda k})$$

$$b_{-\sigma} = \int \frac{d\omega}{2\pi} f_{\lambda}(\omega) 2\pi \sum_{\lambda k} \frac{|V_{\lambda k - \sigma}|^2}{V_{\lambda k}} \delta(\omega - \epsilon_{\lambda k}) g_{\sigma}^a(\omega) + \dots$$

$$\sum_k \frac{1}{\dots}$$

~~$$= \int \frac{d\omega}{2\pi} \sum_{\lambda} R_{\lambda}(\omega) f_{\lambda}(\omega) g_{\sigma}^a(\omega)$$~~

complex

$$g_{\sigma}^a(\omega) = \frac{1}{\omega^2 - \epsilon_{\sigma} + x\gamma_{-\sigma} + (1-x\langle n_{-\sigma} \rangle)^2 \Sigma_{\sigma\sigma}(\omega)}$$

complex

Fowler

(k)

$$i \frac{d n_{\sigma}}{dt} = [n_{\sigma}, H]$$

and

$$[n_{\sigma}, H] = - \sum_{\lambda k} V_{\lambda k \sigma} c_{\lambda k \sigma}^{\dagger} D_{\sigma} + \sum_{\lambda k} V_{\lambda k \sigma}^* D_{\sigma}^{\dagger} c_{\lambda k \sigma}$$

Very important, exact relation valid for in MBL for Hubbard and assisted hopping interactions!

$$i \dot{n}_{\sigma} = [n_{\sigma}, H] = \sum_{\lambda k} \epsilon_{\lambda k} [n_{\sigma}, n_{\lambda k}] + U [n_{\sigma}, n_{\sigma}] + \sum_{\lambda k} V_{\lambda k \sigma} [n_{\sigma}, c_{\lambda k \sigma}^{\dagger} D_{\sigma}] + V_{\lambda k \sigma}^* [n_{\sigma}, D_{\sigma}^{\dagger} c_{\lambda k \sigma}]$$

$$n_{\sigma} c_{\lambda k \sigma}^{\dagger} D_{\sigma} - x n_{\sigma} c_{\lambda k \sigma}^{\dagger} D_{\sigma} n_{\sigma} = - c_{\lambda k \sigma}^{\dagger} D_{\sigma} n_{\sigma} D_{\sigma} - (i) + x c_{\lambda k \sigma}^{\dagger} D_{\sigma} n_{\sigma} D_{\sigma} n_{\sigma} + (i)$$

$$= - \delta_{\sigma} c_{\lambda k \sigma}^{\dagger} D_{\sigma} + x c_{\lambda k \sigma}^{\dagger} D_{\sigma} n_{\sigma} \rightarrow - \delta_{\sigma} c_{\lambda k \sigma}^{\dagger} D_{\sigma}$$

$$[n_{\sigma}, D_{\sigma}^{\dagger} c_{\lambda k \sigma}] \rightarrow D_{\sigma}^{\dagger} D_{\sigma} n_{\sigma} c_{\lambda k \sigma} - (i) = \delta_{\sigma} D_{\sigma}^{\dagger} c_{\lambda k \sigma} + D_{\sigma}^{\dagger} n_{\sigma} c_{\lambda k \sigma} - (i)$$

$$- [n_{\sigma}, D_{\sigma}^{\dagger} c_{\lambda k \sigma} n_{\sigma}] = D_{\sigma}^{\dagger} D_{\sigma} n_{\sigma} c_{\lambda k \sigma} - (i) = \delta_{\sigma} D_{\sigma}^{\dagger} c_{\lambda k \sigma} n_{\sigma} + D_{\sigma}^{\dagger} n_{\sigma} c_{\lambda k \sigma} n_{\sigma} - (i)$$

$$= \delta_{\sigma} D_{\sigma}^{\dagger} c_{\lambda k \sigma}$$

$$[n_{\sigma}, H] = - \sum_{\lambda k} V_{\lambda k \sigma} c_{\lambda k \sigma}^{\dagger} D_{\sigma} + \sum_{\lambda k} V_{\lambda k \sigma}^* D_{\sigma}^{\dagger} c_{\lambda k \sigma}$$

$\rightarrow$ $\begin{matrix} \text{H}_1 \\ \text{H}_2 \\ \text{H}_3 \\ \text{H}_4 \end{matrix}$

(7)

$$i \frac{d\langle n_0 \rangle}{dt} = \sum_{\nu} V_{\nu 0}^* \langle D_0^\dagger C_{\nu 0} \rangle - \sum_{\nu} V_{\nu 0} \langle C_{\nu 0}^\dagger D_0 \rangle$$

Taking average of both sides of the above eqn as $\langle n_0 \rangle$ does not depend on time we find $\langle \frac{d\langle n_0 \rangle}{dt} \rangle = \frac{d\langle n_0 \rangle}{dt} = 0$,

$$\sum_{\nu} V_{\nu 0}^* \langle D_0^\dagger C_{\nu 0} \rangle = \sum_{\nu} V_{\nu 0} \langle C_{\nu 0}^\dagger D_0 \rangle$$

To calculate $\langle D_0^\dagger(t) C_{\nu 0}(t) \rangle = -i \langle \langle C_{\nu 0} | D_0^\dagger \rangle \rangle$
 we need Feynman rules GF. To calculate we first find the action

$$i \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \langle \langle C_{\nu 0}(t) | D_0^\dagger(t) \rangle \rangle = \langle \langle [C_{\nu 0}(t), H] | D_0^\dagger(t) \rangle \rangle = \epsilon_{\nu 0} \langle \langle C_{\nu 0} | D_0^\dagger \rangle \rangle + V_{\nu 0} \langle \langle D_0 | D_0^\dagger \rangle \rangle$$

$$(i \frac{\partial}{\partial t} - \epsilon_{\nu 0}) \langle \langle C_{\nu 0}(t) | D_0^\dagger(t) \rangle \rangle = V_{\nu 0} \langle \langle D_0(t) | D_0^\dagger(t) \rangle \rangle$$

$$\langle \langle C_{\nu 0}(t) | D_0^\dagger(t) \rangle \rangle = V_{\nu 0} \int dt' g_{\nu 0}(t, t') \langle \langle D_0(t') | D_0^\dagger(t') \rangle \rangle$$

$$\langle \langle C_{\nu 0}(t) | D_0^\dagger(t) \rangle \rangle = V_{\nu 0} \int dt' [g_{\nu 0}^r \langle \langle D_0 | D_0^\dagger \rangle \rangle^r + g_{\nu 0}^< \langle \langle D_0 | D_0^\dagger \rangle \rangle^<]$$

$$\langle \langle C_{\nu 0} | D_0^\dagger \rangle \rangle_0^< = V_{\nu 0} [g_{\nu 0}^r \langle \langle D_0 | D_0^\dagger \rangle \rangle_0^< + g_{\nu 0}^< \langle \langle D_0 | D_0^\dagger \rangle \rangle_0^<]$$

Problem 11

(3)

$$\langle c_{\lambda\mu}^\dagger D_\nu \rangle = -i \langle D_\mu | c_{\lambda\sigma}^\dagger(t) \rangle^<$$

$$-i \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \langle \langle D_\sigma(t) | c_{\lambda\sigma}^\dagger(t) \rangle \rangle = - \langle \langle D_\sigma(t) | [c_{\lambda\sigma}^\dagger(t), H] \rangle \rangle$$

$$[c_{\lambda\sigma}^\dagger, H] = -\epsilon_{\lambda\mu} c_{\lambda\sigma}^\dagger - V_{\lambda\mu}^\nu D_\sigma^\dagger$$

$$(-i \frac{\partial}{\partial t} - \epsilon_{\lambda\mu}) \langle \langle D_\sigma(t) | c_{\lambda\sigma}^\dagger(t) \rangle \rangle = V_{\lambda\mu}^\nu \langle \langle D_\sigma(t) | D_\sigma^\dagger(t) \rangle \rangle$$

$$\langle \langle D_\sigma(t) | c_{\lambda\sigma}^\dagger(t) \rangle \rangle = V_{\lambda\mu}^\nu \int dt' \langle \langle D_\sigma(t) | D_\sigma^\dagger(t') \rangle \rangle g_{\lambda\mu}(t, t')$$

$$1 \langle \langle D_\sigma(t) | c_{\lambda\sigma}^\dagger(t) \rangle \rangle = V_{\lambda\mu}^\nu \int dt' | \epsilon_{\lambda\mu} | \langle \langle D_\sigma | D_\sigma^\dagger \rangle \rangle^r g_{\lambda\mu}^< + \langle \langle D_\sigma | D_\sigma^\dagger \rangle \rangle^< g_{\lambda\mu}^e]$$

$$\langle \langle D_\sigma | c_{\lambda\mu}^\dagger \rangle \rangle_\omega = V_{\lambda\mu}^\nu [\langle \langle D_\sigma | D_\sigma^\dagger \rangle \rangle_\omega^r g_{\lambda\mu}^<(\omega) + \langle \langle D_\sigma | D_\sigma^\dagger \rangle \rangle_\omega^< g_{\lambda\mu}^e(\omega)]$$

$$\sum_{\lambda\mu} V_{\lambda\mu}^\nu \langle \langle D_\sigma^\dagger | c_{\lambda\mu} \rangle \rangle = -i \int \frac{d\omega}{2\pi} V_{\lambda\mu}^\nu \langle \langle D_\sigma | D_\sigma^\dagger \rangle \rangle_\omega^< \{ g_{\lambda\mu}^<(\omega) \langle \langle D_\sigma | D_\sigma^\dagger \rangle \rangle_\omega^< + g_{\lambda\mu}^< \langle \langle D_\sigma | D_\sigma^\dagger \rangle \rangle_\omega^< \}$$

$$\textcircled{c} = -i \int \frac{d\omega}{2\pi} \sum_{\lambda\mu} |V_{\lambda\mu}^\nu|^2 \{ g_{\lambda\mu}^<(\omega) \langle \langle D_\sigma | D_\sigma^\dagger \rangle \rangle_\omega^< + g_{\lambda\mu}^< \langle \langle D_\sigma | D_\sigma^\dagger \rangle \rangle_\omega^< \}$$

$$\textcircled{d} = -i \int \frac{d\omega}{2\pi} \sum_{\lambda\mu} |V_{\lambda\mu}^\nu|^2 \{ \langle \langle D_\sigma | D_\sigma^\dagger \rangle \rangle_\omega^r g_{\lambda\mu}^<(\omega) + \langle \langle D_\sigma | D_\sigma^\dagger \rangle \rangle_\omega^< g_{\lambda\mu}^e(\omega) \}$$

$$\int \frac{d\omega}{2\pi} \sum_{\alpha \in \Lambda} |g_{\alpha}^r(\omega) - g_{\alpha}^l(\omega)| \ll D_0 |D_0^+ \gg_{\omega}^r = \int \frac{d\omega}{2\pi} \sum_{\alpha \in \Lambda} |v_{\alpha}|^2 g_{\alpha}^r \ll D_0 |D_0^+ \gg_{\omega}^r - \ll D_0 |D_0^+ \gg_{\omega}^r$$

$$\left(\frac{1}{\omega - \epsilon_{\alpha} + i0} - \frac{1}{\omega - \epsilon_{\alpha} - i0} \right) = -i2\pi \delta(\omega - \epsilon_{\alpha})$$

$$E = -i \int \frac{d\omega}{2\pi} \sum_{\alpha \in \Lambda} |v_{\alpha}|^2 f(\omega - \epsilon_{\alpha}) \ll D_0 |D_0^+ \gg_{\omega}^r =$$

$$= -i \int \frac{d\omega}{2\pi} \sum_{\alpha \in \Lambda} |v_{\alpha}|^2 f(\omega) \ll D_0 |D_0^+ \gg_{\omega}^r \stackrel{UBL}{=} \sum_{\alpha} \Gamma_{\sigma}^{\alpha} \langle D_0^+ D_0 \rangle$$

$$P = i \int \frac{d\omega}{2\pi} \sum_{\alpha \in \Lambda} |v_{\alpha}|^2 f_{\alpha}(\omega) 2\pi \delta(\omega - \epsilon_{\alpha}) [\ll D_0 |D_0^+ \gg_{\omega}^r - \ll D_0 |D_0^+ \gg_{\omega}^r]$$

$$= \int \frac{d\omega}{2\pi} \sum_{\alpha \in \Lambda} \Gamma_{\sigma}^{\alpha} f_{\alpha}(\omega) i [\ll D_0 |D_0^+ \gg_{\omega}^r - \ll D_0 |D_0^+ \gg_{\omega}^r]$$

$$= \int \frac{d\omega}{2\pi} \sum_{\alpha \in \Lambda} \Gamma_{\sigma}^{\alpha} f_{\alpha}(\omega) (-\frac{1}{\hbar}) J_{\alpha} \ll D_0 |D_0^+ \gg_{\omega}^r$$

$$\langle D_0^+ D_0 \rangle = \int d\omega \frac{\sum_{\alpha} \Gamma_{\sigma}^{\alpha} f_{\alpha}(\omega)}{\sum_{\alpha} \Gamma_{\sigma}^{\alpha}} (-\frac{1}{\hbar}) J_{\alpha} \ll D_0 |D_0^+ \gg_{\omega}^r$$

for $x=0$

$$\langle n_{\sigma} \rangle = \int d\omega \frac{\sum_{\alpha} \Gamma_{\sigma}^{\alpha} f_{\alpha}(\omega)}{\sum_{\alpha} \Gamma_{\sigma}^{\alpha}} (-\frac{1}{\hbar}) J_{\alpha} \ll D_0 |D_0^+ \gg_{\omega}^r$$

Prpady $\cup$ (U)

(b) cut

I-

$$\mu_\lambda = \mu + eV_\lambda$$

$$I_\lambda = \frac{2e}{h} \sum_\sigma \int \frac{dE}{2\pi} \Gamma_\sigma^\lambda \left(\frac{\sum_{\lambda'} \Gamma_{\sigma'}^{\lambda'} f_{\lambda'}(E)}{\sum_{\lambda'} \Gamma_{\sigma'}^{\lambda'}} \right) \text{Im} G_\sigma^r(E)$$

Podobnei pyd eicply

$$I_\lambda = \frac{2e}{h} \sum_\sigma \int \frac{dE}{2\pi} \sum_{\sigma'} \Gamma_{\sigma'}^\lambda (E - \mu_\lambda) \left(\frac{\sum_{\lambda'} \Gamma_{\sigma'}^{\lambda'} f_{\lambda'}^*(E)}{\sum_{\lambda'} \Gamma_{\sigma'}^{\lambda'}} \right) \text{Im} G_\sigma^r(E)$$

$\lambda = L, R, U, D$ (= lower)

$$I_{LR} = I_L - I_R$$

$$I_{UD} = I_U - I_D$$

W melimiongu prpcedhu gntoc' stonac na krope, DOS

$$N_\sigma(E) = -\frac{1}{\pi} \text{Im} G_\sigma^r(E, \{V_\lambda\})$$

depends on ~~at~~ voltage bias of each of the terminals

Let write ($\lambda = 0$)

$$F_D = \int \frac{dE}{2\pi} (f_D(E) - f_U(E)) N(E, \{V_{L,R,U,D}\})$$

~~At~~

Open b.c. imply $I_D = I_U = 0 \Rightarrow \mu_D = \mu_U$
(spin dependent)

$$I_D = \frac{2e}{h} \left(\sum_{\sigma} \right) \int \frac{dE}{2\pi} \Gamma^D \left[\frac{\Gamma^L f_L + \Gamma^R f_R + \Gamma^D f_D + \Gamma^U f_U}{\Gamma^L + \Gamma^R + \Gamma^U + \Gamma^D} \right] \times \text{Im } G^r(E)$$

If $I_D = 0$ & $I_U = 0$ then

$$\int dE (f_D(E) - f_U(E)) N(E, \{V_{L,R,U,D}\}) = 0$$

has to vanish

never vanishes
 $f(x) = \frac{1}{e^{(x-\mu)/k_B T} + 1}$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{x - \mu_D}{k_B T_D} = \frac{x - \mu_U}{k_B T_U}$$

For $T_D = T_U = T$

$\mu_D = \mu_U$ no Hell voltage!!

they depend on I_s and V_s

Rect. factor $R_{ij} = \frac{I_{ij}(V) - I_{ij}(-V)}{2}$

to make $R_{ij} > 0$ and $0 < R_{ij} < 1$

Use

$$R_{ij}(V) = \frac{|I_{ij}(V)| - |I_{ij}(-V)|}{|I_{ij}(V)| + |I_{ij}(-V)|}$$

analogous to $\Delta T = T_i - T_j$

Test of symmetry $R_{ij,ke}(I) = -R_{ij,ke}(-I)$
 (cf Butcher in linear limit
 $R_{ij,ke}(I) = R_{ij,ke}(\pm I)$)

$V \rightarrow 0, I \rightarrow 0$

Test: Hall current vs ed. Kondo regime $T=0.01$, $U=12$, $\alpha=1.5$ various voltages V

Departures from linearity
(make it worse!)

